

Bohm Aharonov Effect and Stochastic Potential

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In a previous note (1), we argued that a potential $V(x)$ may be written as $\sum_k V(k) \exp(ikx)$. Thus, $-dV/dx$ is only an average force which may in fact be zero, yet $-d/dx V(k) \exp(ikx)$ is not zero leading to possible forward and backward motion/acceleration (due to each $V(k) \exp(ikx)$ which act at a different times). This gives rise to a momentum distribution $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx)/W(x)$ ($W(x)$ =wavefunction) at each x . In this note, we wish to link these ideas to the Bohm Aharonov effect by considering two recent (2018, 2020) examples from the literature. In the first (2), the magnetic potential $A(r)$ is written in a Fourier series in the same manner as $V(k)\exp(ikx)$. Thus, although $\text{grad } A = B$ (magnetic field) = 0, $\text{grad } A(k) \exp(ikx)$ should not be zero and so there may be hits from “virtual photons”. (2) applies perturbation theory to find a correction to energy E and then considers $\exp(i \int \delta E dt)$ as in adiabatic theory.

The second approach (3) applies the usual Hamiltonian containing the magnetic potential A , but imagines a little box at various x_i positions such that $A(x_i)$ is a constant at each x_i . In such a case, one may show directly that $W(x) = W(x=0) \exp(i e/\hbar \int_{x_0}^{x_1} A(x) dx)$ which yields the Ehrenberg–Siday–Aharonov–Bohm effect. In this approach, one essentially has a different constant potential at each point and hence a different energy. In a previous note, we argued that even though average kinetic energy may remain the same, a change in constant potential using $\sum_k V(k) \exp(ikx)$ gives rise to different physical effects which try to argue are related to the Bohm Aharonov effect. We also try to consider a more general case.

Two Methods For Calculating the Bohm-Aharonov Effect

When calculating phase shifts for a particle in a specific momentum state, $\exp(ikx)$ is often considered and linked to a physical wavelength. We argue that $\exp(iEt)$ is equally physical and is related to internal cycling. In the case of adiabatic theory, a particle in a system which is slowly changing (e.g. a box become slowly longer), remains in its current eigenstate (parametrized by say L the length of the box), but a phase of $\exp(i \int E(t) dt)$ results. The energy changes with the parameter, so E is a function of time. It seems this approach may be applied to a situation where there is no average force (Bohm-Aharonov case with a solenoid), but with the potential changing at each point, causing the energy to change. (2) $\int dt E(t)$ may be changed into a spatial one by using $dt = dx/v$ which is the approach used in (2). Alternatively, one solve a Schrodinger equation containing a potential $V(x)$. One may consider the particle being in equilibrium at each point x_i with $V(x_i)$ being a different constant at each x_i . This leads to a phase factor which is a function of x instead of t , but the idea of an adiabatic change and a change in energy at each x (and hence each t) seems to still hold.

Let us consider the specific approaches of (2) and (3) in more detail. In (2), the potential for a particle moving outside a solenoid where B =magnetic field=0 (and hence magnetic force is 0) is:

$$V(r) = \int d^3r - J(r) \cdot A(r) - q/m p \cdot A(r) + q \int d^3k c_1 [a(k) \exp(ikr) + a^* \exp(-ikr)]$$

Where J , A and p are vectors and c_1 is a constant given in (2).

This potential is written in terms of creation and annihilation operators (i.e. a Fourier series) and perturbation theory is used to calculate ΔE to second order (because the first order correction vanishes). In other words, even though there is no force, energy is still changing in space. The phase factor $\exp(i \int dt E(t))$, identical to that of an adiabatic process, is used as the idea seems to be that the particle is in an equilibrium state with energy $E + \Delta E(t)$ at each t and hence each x . ΔE is given by $A(x) p$ where $\text{curl } A = B$ and p is the momentum. The momentum is then written as $m dx/dt$ and so $\int dt m dx/dt = m \int dx$ i.e. one obtains a path integral in space.

In (3), the approach is to consider the Schrodinger equation for the solenoid case as:

$$\frac{1}{2m} [-i \hbar \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} - e/c A(x)]^2 W(x) + U(x) W(x) = E W(x) \quad ((1))$$

Here $A(x)$ is the magnetic potential ($B = \text{curl } A$) and $U(x)$ represents infinite walls as the authors assume that one has a particle in a tiny box with infinite walls which moves from one x point to another. At each x point the potential created by $A(x)$ is a constant i.e. $d/dx A(x) = 0$. Thus, one has a particle in a box with infinite walls and a different constant potential in the box at each x . This is again similar to an adiabatic process (like in (2)), but ((1)) may be solved explicitly yielding:

$$W(x) = W(0) \exp(i e/\hbar c \int_{x=x_0}^{x=x_1} A(x) dx) \quad ((2)) \text{ where } A(0)=0$$

Thus, a phase is obtained. It should be noted that $W(x)$ is complex, so this is not a bound state solution which seems to be fine because the particle is moving in one direction. One may also think of the particle in the box moving in one direction i.e. the solution of $\exp(ikx)$ and not $\cos(kx)$. Thus, one argues that expanding the square term in ((1)) and treating A as a constant leads to a momentum dependent potential which is equivalent to writing $\frac{1}{2m} p^* p [\exp(i B(x)) W(x)] = E W(x)$. In other words, it is as if one transforms $W_1 = \exp(i B(x)) W$, so that W_1 is a solution of: $p^* p/2m W_1 = E W_1$. Such a transformation does not affect the spatial density. This is keeping with the adiabatic approximation. It is also in keeping with the idea in (3) that changing V constant from one value to another for a particle in a box with an infinite potential at the walls does not change the wavefunction (except by a phase).

Transformation Approach

Consider a particle moving through space with no force (or potential). Then:

$$p^* p/2m W(x) = E W(x) \text{ where } \exp(ikx) \text{ or } \exp(-ikx) \text{ is a solution. } \quad ((1b))$$

Next, consider a phase added to such a wavefunction of the form $\exp(i B(x))$. This phase does not affect the spatial density $W^* W$ which is considered to be a physical observable. It does, however, affect the momentum distribution $P(p/x)$. Usually, this is $\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)/W(x)$, but now with the new wavefunction, it changes. This suggests that microscopic motions and forward/backward forces are in play such that the overall average force is 0. If one expands ((1b)), one obtains a Schrodinger equation with an explicit potential (actually momentum dependent potential), but there is no average force. This is similar to the idea of having a particle in a box with infinite walls and changing V constant in the box.

Comparison with the (1)

In (1), we discussed a model in which $V(x)$ and $-d/dx V(x)$ are averages with $V(x)=\sum_k V(k) \exp(ikx)$. Thus on average, one may have $-d/dx V(x)=0$ and $KE(x)$ average constant even though much microscopic activity occurs. One may have forward and backward force hits at different times as long as the average is 0. If V is a constant, different values of $V(x_i)$ lead to different forward and backward motion even though $KE(x)$ average does not change. The overall energy, however, changes if $V(x_i)$ constant changes. This seems to match the situation in (2) and (3). Thus, force does not seem to completely govern the Schrodinger equation, rather the Fourier transform of the potential is more important. Constant V means no average force, but the Fourier series of different V constant values differ and so we argue, the physical microscopic motion should also differ even though the wavefunction (for a box with infinite walls) remains unchanged i.e. $\exp(ipx)$. If one has such a scenario even for V constant, one may envision microscopic changes as the particle changes from one constant potential region to another as argued in (1). Thus, it is not only the step function at the walls which is important. For the case of (3), where the particle is in a box with a different V constant values at each x , one may argue that the overall $V(x)$ looks like many step functions as each different V constant. The Fourier transform of this situation would indicate microscopic $\exp(ikx)$ motion, which ultimately seems to yield the Bohm-Aharonov phase.

More General Case

Consider first a more general example, such that:

$W_1(x) = W(x) \exp(i B(x))$ where $B(x) = \int_{x_1=0}^x G(x_1) dx_1$ and:

$\frac{p^2}{2m} W_1 = E W_1$. Thus, W_1 is like a free quantum particle moving in one direction in space, but has an extra phase dependent on x . Expand the Schrodinger equation to obtain:

$$\frac{p^2}{2m} W + \left(\frac{p^2}{2m} W \right) (i G(x)) - \frac{W}{2m} (i dG/dx) + \frac{1}{2m} G^*G = E W \quad ((4b))$$

In the approach of (3), one sets $dG/dx=0$ even though $G(x)$ is not a constant. It is considered to be a constant at each point x in space. Thus, one performs a kind of adiabatic expansion, otherwise one has a complex potential term.

Thus, one may have a more general equation which uses $G(x)$ instead of $A(x)$, assuming that there is a physical situation which actually utilises ((4b)) as a Schrodinger equation.

Consider a different problem, namely a Schrodinger equation with a potential $V(x)$ such that $-d/dx V(x) = 0$ everywhere. Thus, $V(x)$ should be a constant, but imagine that in the spirit of (3) one has different $V(x_i)$ at different places. The average KE(x) remains constant (because there is no average force). In other words, an adiabatic scenario is applied such that the V_i constants change slowly and gradually. One may then ask whether there is an expression:

$$W_1 = W_0 \exp(iB(x)) \text{ such that } p^2/2m W_0 = E_0 W_0$$

In other words, can one obtain a phase moving through space which is equivalent to $V(x)$ real?

Then:

$$p^2/2m W - 1/m [dW/dx + i dB/dx] - i/2m W d/dx d/dx B + 1/m (dB/dx)(dB/dx) W + VW = EW \quad ((5))$$

$$\text{If } B = \int_{x_1=0}^x G(x_1) dx_1 \text{ then } dB/dx = G(x)$$

In keeping with (3), one needs to set $d/dx d/dx B = 0$ in order to avoid a complex potential. In such a case, with $dW/dx = ik W$ (i.e. $W = \exp(ikx)$)

$$1/m k G + 1/m G^2 + V = 0 \quad ((6))$$

Thus, if one may find a G such that ((6)) holds, then one may apply the Bohm-Aharonov effect to other cases than the electromagnetic one. In this more general case, we use an explicit form for W , namely $\exp(ikx)$ and $d/dx W$ does not cancel as in the electromagnetic case.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to argue that two recent approaches related to the Bohm-Aharonov effect ((2) from 2020 and (3) from 2018) are similar to ideas proposed in (1), namely that $V(x) = \sum_k V(k) \exp(ikx)$. In such a case, each $V(k) \exp(ikx)$ may give rise to different k momentum hits at different times, but on average the force is $-dV/dx$. If this average force is 0, there are still forward and backward hits from the $V(k) \exp(ikx)$. In particular, if one has different V_{constant} values at different x_i points, the Fourier transform changes suggesting different physical behaviour, namely $\Delta \text{Work} = - \int V(k) \exp(ikx) dx$. For different $V(k)$ i.e. different V_{constant} ,

the work is different. Thus, we argue that the approach of (1) is consistent with those of (2) and (3) and gives a physical picture of the underlying microscopic behaviour. In (2), the microscopic behaviour is described as the action of virtual photons which seems to be consistent with (2).

We also try to consider a more general case, using $W_1 = W \exp(i B(x))$ to see if one may transform: $\frac{p^2}{2m} W_1 + V W_1 = E W_1$ (with $V(x)$ constant and slowly increasing so the adiabatic approach holds) into: $\frac{p^2}{2m} W = E W$.

References

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